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Folk/Subaltern Religion and Development

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Abstract: This paper deals with the proactive role of *folk religions* in the evolving concept of 'development'. It dwells on the various possibilities of interaction between the two at different levels and between their different aspects, bringing into dialogue two seemingly contradictory historical human initiatives: the phenomenon of folk religion which is often regarded as pre-modern, and the idea of development which is conceptually intertwined with the process of modernisation. While the latter is taken to mean primarily the economic disillusionment, the article takes into account other models of development evolved in the last few decades, in which the concept has undergone change and the horizons of its understanding have expanded to include the overall well-being of humans. This article has two parts: *part one* focuses on the nature and dynamics of the relationship between the economic terrain of development and the phenomenon of folk/subaltern religion, and *part two* dwells on the new meanings of development, and the mediating role that the folk religions can play both at the conceptual and the concrete levels of such development schemes.

Keywords: Folk religions, subalternity, rural religiosity, urban religiosity, equality.

This article endeavours to investigate the question of the relationship between folk or subaltern religion and development, bringing into dialogue two seemingly contradictory historical human initiatives: the phenomenon of folk religion which is often regarded as pre-modern, and the idea of development which is conceptually intertwined with the process of modernisation. While the latter is taken to mean primarily the economic dimension, the article takes into account other models of development evolved in the last few decades, in which the concept has undergone change and the horizons of its understanding have expanded to include the overall well-being of humans, as many authors have pointed out. Subsequently, the article has two parts: *part one* which focuses on the nature and dynamics of relationship between the economic terrain of development and the phenomenon of folk/subaltern religion, and *part two* which dwells on the new meanings of development, and the mediating role that the folk religions can play both at the conceptual and the concrete levels of such development schemes.

Part I

1. Folk Religion and Economic Development

Though today's understanding of development means more than the economic aspect, yet we need to take up the relationship of folk religion and development not only because Weber's theory of religion, which remains very influential till today, focuses on the relationship between religion and economic development, but also because most of the social scientists following Weber have found Hinduism as obstructing development. For instance K.W Kapp² held that the general beliefs and values of Hinduism like the law of karma and astrology denied history its transformative role in social and economic development. Another writer, Mishra, attempts to establish that the other-worldliness of Hinduism stresses the release from the cycle of rebirth, and this, he believes, has adversely affected economic growth. While we cannot take up this issue in detail, the questions that need to be asked are "Are these observations true? Are they applicable to the whole of Hinduism? Or to part of it? What brand of Hinduism if any is anti-development?" Is the kind of Hinduism that we are interested in, namely, folk religion against development? or does it promote development?

While scrutinising the relationship between Hinduism and economic development, most of the authors following the hypothetico-deductive method have derived their conclusions from the abstract ideas of higher Hinduism's values which are either favourable or unfavourable to economic development. Such conclusions deduced from beliefs and values of the conceptual domain remain alienated from concrete social and cultural contexts. Instead, one has to shift the focus from text-bound Hinduism to practice-oriented Hinduism. The latter includes not only the practices of the elite Brahminic order, but also the rituals of the ordinary common folk. "In considering Hinduism in relation to economic growth, the character of the former as it is practiced by the common people is more important than its metaphysical aspects."³

The common people's folk ritual observances and practices such as vows and votive offerings and a consideration of these in relation to economic activities present a different perspective on the relationship between religion and economic action. Rao notes that people keep the *vratas* to various folk deities not only in the rural areas but also in the urban habitats, in order to seek benefits which are often mundane and material.

In the folk religious practices, a worshipper is promised success and prosperity in this world, and often such mundane prosperities are regarded to be the result of accumulated ritual merit. The folk gods and goddesses are perceived to have enormous powers over the prosperity of the village and the fertility of the village lands. These deities who represent the powers of nature offer not only promises and assurances to people to improve their economic lot in the agrarian settings, but also hope to those who have failed in business or who seek employment. "The ritual practices seeking the divine assistance in achieving a specific objective belong to the realm of religion and they seek to establish a bridge between the mundane activity on the one hand and supernatural beings on the other."⁴ This integrating function of folk rituals enables the common folk to harmoniously reconcile the needs and demands of modern life with their day-to-day living through their belief in the powers of gods and goddesses.

Thus, contrary to popular belief, the folk ritual observances and practices emphasise the this-worldly aspect of Hinduism, which has been ignored by those who have written on Hinduism and economic development. Ritual practice, often enacted through the folk religious realm, “emphasising the worldly character of Hinduism acts as a corrective to the hypothetico-deductive view of the other-worldliness of Hinduism. But this worldliness of Hinduism does not by itself guarantee a positive orientation to economic action”⁵ As Rao rightly observes whether ritual promotes an outlook for the positive pursuit of economic activities is a question which requires empirical investigation.⁶

2. Folk/Subaltern Religion and the Process of Modernity

In the sociological studies of religions in India, folk religions are generally treated as pre-modern or mere remnant of the old feudal system, and as static or stagnant with the mechanical routinisation of their rituals. The latest studies on the folk and subaltern religions conducted in their socio-economic-historical milieus take issue with such understandings.

My own research done on the folk religious phenomenon of Sudalaimadan Cult in Tirunelveli district of Tamilnadu has contested such a view. The study has shown that in the origin and growth of a folk religious phenomenon such as Sudalaimadan cult changes can occur in the symbolic meaning schemes as a result of the *advent of modernity*. It has indicated how old religio-cultural forms can obtain new schemes of socio-economic meanings in course of history.

The changes in the district occurred following the initial phase of modernization inaugurated by the British in the nineteenth century in this region. The policy decisions regarding land-holdings, new revenue systems (such as *ryotwari*), education, employment, market, etc., made by the colonial state brought about transformation not only in the socio-economic systems, but subsequently, it became a collateral factor for the emergence of different folk religious forms. It was not a mere change that took place in the past and was pertinent only to a particular point of time in history. It was not experienced as a residual phenomenon that passed away along with the death of the colonial state. The changes brought about by the

colonial state were carried out by the independent Indian state which has carried over the impact of modernity to the present. Modernization has undoubtedly acquired new accents and varied emphases through different economic systems such as capitalism, liberalisation and globalisation, but has also yielded different benefits to different sections within the caste hierarchy. The different agents of change have provided impetus to different actors by bringing in alternative economic systems and schemes at different times, and, through them, new opportunities for the liberation of the subalterns from the old economic system of caste hierarchy. Thus, it has effected a change in society over a period of time. All these phenomena have brought about not only fluidity within the socio-economic systems but also transformations in the religious systems such as folk religions.

The study shows that by making use of temple honours and the nuances of ritual power, social actors can articulate the newly acquired symbolic power. It has been appropriated by different social actors across the spectrum of the caste hierarchy at different times in different intensities. The changes experienced by the people by their appropriation of new systems have shown up in the symbolic universe. New cohorts of castes and families have appropriated the subaltern religious terrain and generated new forms of socio-symbolic discourse in the district of Tirunelveli. They have not drastically altered the folk forms of worship, but have infused new social meanings into the old symbolic systems. Thus they have altered the old cultural conceptual schemes and meaning systems in the ever-growing new contexts, be it the colonial state, independent India, or the global world. Here, modernity, through various agents such as the colonial state, the independent state and the global world order, has provided new socio-economic constructs to social actors within the caste hierarchy. They, in turn, have apprehended and appropriated the benefits and the privileges of such contexts on the one hand, and, in the process of social transformations, have constructed, constituted, adduced, disseminated and explored new systems of meanings to old religious forms, and have created new socio-symbolic cultural discourses, on the other.

The study has thus unfolded the interplay between culture and modernity in the domain of folk religious cults, in the process of

demonstrating ‘how the symbolic can mirror – and can be mirrored by – the subtle transformations in culture and society.’ It shows that, through the medium of a subaltern religious universe, folk culture can provide new cultural schemes to the subalterns to display new forms of power acquired by the appropriation of the benefits of modernity and industrialisation. Thus modernity has its insidious effects on the delicate balance of power relations within the caste hierarchy, and can become a partner with religion and culture to generate new texts of discourse of symbolic power. It is to be noted that, as modernity can add colours to religion, so, too, culture and religion can add new shades of meaning to the thesis of modernity.

Saurabh Dube, in his seminal study on the history of a subaltern religious sect of the Chamars known as Satnamis, has nuanced the relationship between folk/subaltern religion and modernity further. He has held that through religion arena, the subaltern communities can also engage in construction of creative cartographies defining spaces in time and places in history.⁷

In the above mentioned work, Dube shows that the subaltern Satnamis, while challenging the terms of ritual power and caste hierarchy, colonial authority and nationalist imperatives, can carve out their own visions, designs and practices surrounding sect and caste, myth and history, highlighting the interplay and interpenetration between symbols of modern state and forms of communities in India. Thus, as he claims, he has tapped the potentiality of subaltern religious domain to suggest the importance of linkages between the pre-colonial, colonial and the post-colonial. To achieve this, he has followed the method of conducting fieldwork in an engagement with the historical imagination which addresses the key analytical relationships between sect and caste, myth and history, religion and power, gender and order, community and hegemony, resistance and domination.⁸

Thus, Dube would claim that the entangled endeavours of ethnographic histories and untouchable pasts is capable of unravelling process “involving myths and the making of modernities, orality and the construction of histories, writing and the fashioning of traditions to interrogate the place and persistence of binary categories—of modernity and tradition, state and community, rationality

and ritual, reason and emotion—within influential strands of social and political theory.”⁹ His work calls into question the taken-for-granted overarching opposition between tradition and modernity, “which is often accompanied and animated—at the very least implicitly—by equally grand divisions between myth and history, ritual and reason, magic and the modern.”¹⁰ These binary schemes and categories are actually rooted in reified representation of a singular modernity. The study of subaltern religions in India has unfolded the power of the subaltern religious initiatives to question such conceptions of singular modernity. Thus the historical phenomena of subaltern religions is perceived to have the potentialities to expose the falsity of a representation of modernity, to put it in the words of Saurabh Dube himself, “as a self-realising project of progress, a self-evident embodiment of development and a self-contained incarnation of history.”¹¹

3. Public Sphere, Folk Religion and Modernity

The concept of public sphere as proposed by Habermas meant “a domain of social life in which such a thing as public opinion can be formed A portion of the public opinion is constituted in every conversation in which private persons come together to form a public. Citizens act as a public when they deal with matters of general interest without being subject to coercion.... The coercive power of the state is the counterpart, as it were, of the political public sphere, but not part of it.”¹² In his opinion, public sphere is a mediating category between the civil society and the state. To our Indian context, we have to broaden the outreach of this concept so as to include public spheres other than those envisaged by Habermas, and focus upon the multiplicity and plurality of spheres as well as groups that create them. There is no single monolithic public sphere as there is not single monolithic notion of civil society. Different socio-historical conditions generate multiple spheres and public groups that are engaged in the continuous process of defining and redefining the state and the individual, the caste-hierarchy and the marginal castes. With the production of new and altered symbolic cultural schemes, the subalterns raise voice that transcends hierarchical boundaries of gender and caste through the medium of folk religion and folklore. Folklore and folk ritual performances serve as a me-

dium for contesting dominant world-views. Through them public opinions are generated, discussed and debated. They could be used for articulating heterogeneity rather than stressing homogeneity.¹³ Study of folklore and folk religious forms can reveal how communities can break hierarchies, articulate aspirations and constitute new identities. As identities are constantly created and recreated, what we encounter through the generation of such folk forms is a complex cultural phenomenon “not necessarily rational but in alignment with the logic of cultures concerned. Such process do create and influence public opinion.”¹⁴ As Muthukumar notes, what we see here is a ‘performing society’ that generates public opinion not necessarily through rational verbal arguments and dialogues but *also through gestures, genres, versions, performances, stories, narratives and codes.*¹⁵

Besides, public sphere plays a vital role in the process of modernisation. The changes that modernity brings in its wake become more socially acceptable and the conflicts that are created find a medium in public sphere through which they can be resolved. The various folk forms, including folk religious performances, provide and create public sphere in India, and they help in bringing into focus ideas, values and contentions into public discourse, a kind of unshackling of inhibitions in a stress-free manner.¹⁶ Here folk religion functions as a notable instance in which the creation and sustenance of public sphere becomes significant to achieve the multi-level interests of different performers and patrons.¹⁷

Thus, in some cases, the folk religious arena is perceived to have undergone a shift from the usually ‘private sacred space’ to a site of construction of what can be called “public sphere.” As Bhaduri notes in the case of the origin of community Durga¹⁸ Pooja in 18th and 19th century Bengal, such public spheres arose in the process of the modernisation process initiated by the British. As the author observes, it evolved “in response to the colonial state machinery and often included subversive strategies.”¹⁹ The fact that Raja Nabo Kissen Deb in 18th cent. celebrated Robert Clive over the Muslim ruler, Shiraz-ud-dowla with Durga Puja indicates that the Hindu upper class took the opportunity of British control over Bengal to demonstrate its negative reaction to its erstwhile repression under

Muslim domination. Keeping in line with their general policy that the British would not meddle much in the religious affairs of the natives, they abolished the festival tax introduced by the Muslim rulers. However, the British also introduced a more rigid system of taxation, which means the Zamindars had to pay more to the new masters. But, making use of the privileges and freedom given by the British in religious matters, “an annual extravagant event like the Durga Puja became an easy route for Zamindars to get major tax reliefs and even manage extra allowances from the British.”²⁰ Thus folk or popular religious practices have the potential of becoming an interface between the modern state and civil society, “in this case between the emergent British colonial state and the Hindu Bengali religio-cultural space.”²¹

4. Folk Religion as a Counter-Public and Identity Politics:

One of the social consequences of development and modernisation in India today is the identity politics of religion and caste which is often displayed in the religious realm, more so in the case of folk religious realm. Kaushal, who made a study on the Gaddi community in the western Himalayas, notes that “another very important sub-text of public ritual performances is construction and presentation of a group’s identity to oneself and to others.”²² Blackburn, who made a study on the folk religious performances of South India, also arrives at a similar conclusion. According to her, folk performances “help to shape a community’s self identity” and “they have that special ability to tell a community’s own story and thus help to create and maintain that community’s self-identity.”²³

Now, folk religion’s capacity to construct and uphold the identity of a social group is appropriated by different groups with ingenuity to display their social status and to assert their identity. For instance, the folk cults/ folk rituals like *Kodai* in the southern part of India can become the site of assertion of the newly gained autonomy of the depressed classes in this district, as insightfully shown by Diane P.Mines in a recent study.²⁴ She has demonstrated that identity politics has not only impacted upon the meta-narrative of Hindutva but also has transformed the folk religious arena into a site of contestation by the subalterns who dared to defy caste-hierar-

chy empowered by the newly gained economic status thanks to modernity and its fruits such as education and employment. She explains how the people of Yanaimangalam in Tirunelveli district drew on regional and national socio-politico-religious movements, and contested the social and spatial contours of their local lives and their villages through ritual action.

Making a study on the folk community festivals called *jatar*(s) in the western region of Himalayas, Kaushal holds that while *Bharmour jatar* and *Chchatarari jatar* were the community festivals of the dominant castes in the region, the *Guggal jatar*—celebrated by low caste Halis and Rehars created a space for the articulation of voices of protest against mistreatment and neglect, and can be “generative of multiple public spheres that may use the language of myth and ritual, which seem to overlap, but nonetheless facilitate articulation of counter-hegemonic voices that contest and compete.”²⁵ He concludes that the public sphere created through the medium of folk religious rituals, rather than defusing boundaries may actually become arenas for public display of hostilities and tension that exist in the society.²⁶

Thus, in our contemporary times, the public sphere of folk religions is bound to have within itself fissures and spaces for subversive appropriation leading to the possibility of counter-public

Ambivalent Character of Folk Religion in Urban India

Folk Religions, especially in the urban setting of today’s India, can be described to have ambivalent picture. On the one hand, you have folk temples in the urban setting, which seeks to transcend the boundaries of caste, gender and religion. For instance, Kalpagam, having made a study on roadside temples in the urban areas, observes that, the creation of an urban popular culture through roadside temple activities is an expression of working class culture that seeks to synthesise the Hinduism of the “great tradition” and “little tradition,” and in its everyday practices transcends caste, class, religious and gender boundaries. “It is also simultaneously the constitution of a social text that allows people to draw meanings of nationhood and their sense of belonging in cultural terms that are rooted in local practices, everyday life and localities, and seeks to evolve

new perspectives and ideas of a secular society” This signifies the harmonious side of evolving civil society in the cities and towns.

On the other hand, we can also witness the opposite characteristics of folk religions. Folk religious forms, which assert caste-identity as noted earlier in the article, can also function as a source of subaltern agency. In some urban settings, they can operate as an instrument of negotiating civil space through creation of folk or popular religious sites such as the celebration of ‘Kanwad’²⁷ in cities like Delhi. These religious sites are fundamentally ritual domains wherein, through the rituals, people display their identity, re-member themselves into the cultural habitus they belong to, draw resources to face life, and sometimes even negotiate a new civil space according to their terms.

The above mentioned presence of such contradictory characteristics reveals the ambivalent portrait of folk religions in India. But, in as much as the Indian society that we live in has ambivalent characteristics of equality and discrimination, harmony and conflict, folk religions can be found to depict them in the religious realm. Thus the opposite functions of folk religion can be described to mirror the society which is in conflict itself.

Part II

In this Part, let me deal with the different meanings that the concept of development has acquired over a period of time and the new areas of interaction such new understandings can create for the folk religious phenomenon to engage in the process of development.

1. The Development of ‘development’

We are at the cross-road now in our vision and practice of development. Much of our difficulties here relate to our inability to look at and participate in the field of relationship and as a quest of a shared responsibility which brings the self and the other together. The project of development has been subjected to much criticism and rethinking in the recent years in the midst of which agenda of development has been broadened to include human development from mere economic development and rise in per capita income.²⁸

The above quotation shows us the shifts that have taken place in the very conception of 'development.' In order to have a better grasp of the problematic of development, let me dwell briefly on the history of development.

The concept of 'development' meant different things to different people at different times. Authors identify three post-World War II phases of development. In the first phase (1947-1949), the liminal phase between the World War and the beginning of the cold war, the world grappled with the future after an extreme crisis. In this period, development was seen as a 'work of hope.'²⁹ It primarily aimed at alleviating poverty. It did not go beyond economic growth. In the second phase (1949 –), of the cold war, development entered the domain of politics , application and administration. In 1960, development was defined as 'growth with change,' referring to economic and cultural change, influenced by structural functionalism.³⁰ Development thus meant a simultaneous transformation in all these dimensions. In the mid 1970s, there again occurred a shift of focus of development which aimed at a decent standard of living for all humans, in line with the basic human rights as defined in the UN charter, and measured by 'human development indicators.'³¹ In the third phase (1990-), the natural environment and its ecology became integrated into the development discourse, and 'sustainable development' became the watchword. Sustainable development drew attention to formerly ignored marginal regions and people, like the gold miners in the Amazon, the peasants in Africa, the hill tribes in Thailand etc., who were previously rather ignored.³² Development had little to do with equity, justice or with people and social relations since the subject matter at that time was growth and not distribution. It was in this context that the UN General Assembly resolution called for the renewal of political will to invest in people and their well-being in what could be the trend setter for the next millennium, and set up a special committee in the year 2000 to review the process of development.³³ Following these, a whole array of new discourses of development, such as Amartya Sen's idea of development as freedom (i.e., development as expansion of substantive freedom to achieve alternative functions), development as human dignity and human rights,³⁴ development as 'global responsi-

bility,' and development as cultivation of 'self'³⁵ etc., has acquired significance in the development theories.

Folk/Subaltern Religion as a Process of Development in the Restoration of Equality for All and Human Dignity of the Oppressed

As Aloysius notes, in the subaltern religions, there is a privileging of the ethical over the transcendental and they are often manifestations of voluntary construction of the morally just in place of involuntary acceptance of the 'religiously given' as found in the case of dominant religions. "These transitions need not only be seen as historical, that is, from pre-modernity to modernity, in religion. They are, in fact, dimensions or aspects of religion of all times."³⁶ No doubt one immediately tends to link development of the ethically religious worldview, embodying a social order that is egalitarian, with the emergence of modernity and its democratic institutions. But there were in the pre-modern times protest religious movements in India proposing an ethical world-view, although they came to be subordinated and often submerged as we see in the example of Buddhism in India.

These types of religious movements strive for collective emancipation rather than individual salvation. It has "the power of motor force moving a collectivity to effect a change in human-social reality, a change that takes the reality nearer to the conceptual ideality"³⁷ But in the emancipation of the collective, the human and the dignity of the individual human is restored developed and constructed. The historical examples of The Satnami movement, which reformed the lives of the Chamars in Chattisgarh, Ayyavazhi Movement that transformed the status of Nadars in Kannyakumari District in Tamilnadu, the Narayanguru movement which revolted against the oppression of Ezhavas in Kerala reveal the fact that religion can function as a subaltern agency to defy the oppressive social order, to negotiate a new egalitarian social identity and to restore the human dignity of the oppressed

But not all folk religious phenomena such as CM cult in Tamilnadu, Virabhadra cult in Andhra Pradesh etc, could fit into this type. These pre-modern cults have not emerged as a separate

and a distinct subaltern religious phenomena. But they are sites of contestation of the dominant religious ideology. In fact, both these types contest the hierarchy and both embody the aspirations of the oppressed for liberation from the clutches of gruesome caste hierarchy.

Folk Religion: An Idiom of Reversal ?

Kaulpagam, in his/her study on roadside temples in Chennai, takes note of a case in which the poor auto drivers have employed a Brahmin as a priest wherein the high caste Brahmin is made answerable and accountable to the low caste men. My own PhD research in the district of Trinvelveli on Folk Religion reveals that a good number of most backward castes get the Brahmin priests to perform rituals in their folk temples. Through such folk religious sites, there is a reversal of social dynamics as regards the construction of human dignity in the Indian society. In the traditional agrarian Indian society, the Sanskritic Hinduism had provided a socio-economic structure through its caste-hierarchy wherein the Brahmin-Kshatriya alliance had the power of determining the human dignity of the Sudras and Dalits. The self-worth of a Sudra or a Dalit or his/her self perception was dependent upon the kind of treatment meted out to him/her but within the parameters of caste-hierarchy. The Dalits and Sudras always remained dependent on and accountable to the high castes. In folk religious realm today, on the contrary, as we see in the case of a Brahmin above, the Sudras/Dalit (the auto drivers in Chennai or the most backward castes in Trinvelveli district) have a significant role to play in the self-making of a Brahmin priest. The Brahmin priest in Chennai openly acknowledged this. Kaulpagam writing about him says, "Post-retirement employment as a priest of a roadside temple is really the fulfilment of a long-long yearning as in his youth he was trained in a gurukulam in Mahabalipuram on Agama sastras." While such occurrences point to the new kind of social dynamics that take place in the folk religious realm, they also mirror the subtle social transformations that could occur in the process of development like modernisation or urbanisation and folk religion's potentiality in being instrumental to bring about such transformations.

Folk Religion and Holistic Development

Another major step in the evolution of the concept of 'development' is the realisation that care of the human is intrinsically related to the care of nature. The actualisation of the human cannot take place in isolation or in the abstract. It has to take place in the concrete material world and along with the other creatures and beings in the world. This implies that, during the process of transformation of the humans, the human beings have to work for the promotion of well-being for the whole of the cosmos. While such a task calls for a proactive involvement of the humans in the world, it implies a total rejection of any dichotomy between matter and spirit, sacred and profane. This entails a holistic view of the universe which underscores a fundamental unity between the humans and the cosmos. This basic unity and the symbiotic relationship between the humans and the cosmos is best inscribed, created and established in the embodied human beings through concrete human practices. Such human practices obtain religious overtones in most of the cultures wherein the sacred character of nature is made aware of through folk religious rituals. For instance, Madhu Kanna holds that the folk festival of *navapatrika* worship can be related to the issues of ecological sensibility.³⁸ Similarly the various folk festivals such as *karam* in the tribal belt of Chotanagpur, *kodai* in South India and various season-transition festivals in different parts of India are at once the expressions of the religious and the ecological concerns of the common folk. Folk religious rituals such as *Bihu* in Assam or *Pongal* in Tamilnadu play a major role in making humans realise the inalienable relationship between nature and humans. More often than not, religious beliefs/practices and the earth's ecology are inextricably linked, and organically related. "Religious beliefs—especially those concerning the nature of powers that create and animate—become an effective part of ecological systems."³⁹ Rather than the major religious traditions, it is the folk/indigenous religious traditions which ensure the creation and the maintenance of the human being's intrinsic relationship with the natural environment.

Conclusion

This paper which has attempted to discourse on the proactive role of *folk religions* in the evolving concept '*development*' has dwelt on the various possibilities of interaction between the two at different levels and between their different aspects. Since both these realities have been undergoing evolution themselves in human history, the attempt of discourse, like that of this paper, on interaction between the two can never get exhausted, but rather will remain open-ended.

Notes

1. Folk religions stand for the original religious representations and categories of the non-twice born and non-brahminic masses (Sudras and Dalits), found in the agrarian setting. Unlike Sanskritic Hinduism, folk religions are centred on gods who are carnivorous, and served by priests who are non-Brahmins. Folk religions are believed to have their origin in the feudal system. When a folk religious phenomenon becomes for a subordinate group a site of assertion of their identity and of negotiation with the dominant (the powerful) social groups, be it in the rural and in the urban setting, in the past or in the contemporary time, we can name that religion as subaltern religion.
2. Kapp, K.W, *Hindu Culture, Economic Development and Economic Planning in India*, Asia Publishing House, Bombay, 1963.
3. M.S.A. Rao, "Religion and Economic Development" in Rowena Robinson (ed.,) *Sociology of Religion in India*, Sage Publications, New Delhi, 2004, 68-83, p.74.
4. *Ibid*, p.78.
5. *Ibid.*, p.79.
6. *Ibid*. p. 79.
7. Dube, *Untouchable Pasts*, State University of New York Press, Albany, 1998, p. xii
8. Cf. Dube "Entangled Endeavours," in *PostColonial Passages*, edited by Dube, Oxford University Press, New Delhi, 2004, pp. 196-209.
9. *Ibid.*, p. 209.
10. *Ibid.*, p.206.
11. *Ibid*.

12. Habermas, "The Public Sphere" in Habermas, *Kultur and Kritik*, Trans.S.W. Nicholson in Paul Marris and Sue Thornham , eds. *Media Studies: A Reader*, Edinburgh University Press, Edinburgh, 1996. p. 55.
13. Muthukumarasamy & Molly, "Introduction" in (eds.), *Folklore, Public Sphere and Civil Society*, IGNCA, New Delhi, 2004, 1-16, p.3.
14. *Ibid.*, p.4.
15. *Ibid.* p.3.
16. Bhattacharya, "Preface,"
16. Muthukumarasamy & Molly (eds.), *Folklore*, IX-X.
17. *Ibid.*
18. One might wonder if Durga is a folk deity, as it is often associated with Kali. But the characteristics of the folk deity is clearly seen in Durga. Bhaduri observes that Durga has no permanent temple to her credit and can be worshipped only once a year as a temporarily sculpted idol in temporarily erected community pandals under a temporarily festive public gaze, and a Durga puja is an annually generated mass activity and not a solipsistic religious function. Cf. Bhaduri, "Of Public Sphere and Sacred Space: Origin of Community Durga Puja in Bengal," in Muthukumarasamy & Molly (eds.), *Folklore*, pp 77-89, p. 80.
19. *Ibid.* p. 7.
20. *Ibid.*, p.82.
21. *Ibid.*, p. 88.
22. Kaushal, , "From Mythic to Political Identities: Folk Festivals and Cultural Sub-texts," in Muthukumarasamy & Molly (eds.), *Folklore*, pp 186-196. p. 187.
23. Blackburn et al., *Oral Epics in India*, University of California Press, Berkeley, 1989, p. 11.
24. Diane P Mines in "Hindu Nationalism, Untouchable reform, and ritual production of a South Indian Village," *American Ethnologist*, Vol 29, No;1, Feb. 2002.
25. Kaushal, *From Mythic.*, p. 194.
26. *Ibid.*
27. Naresh Goswami notes that the celebration of this festival has as much to do with religion as an assertion of identity in urban social dynam-

- ics. Cf. "Songs of the Road," in *The Times of India*, August, 17, 2005, 14.
28. Ananta Kumar Giri, *New Horizons of Social Theory*, Jaipur: Rawat Publications, 2006. p.200.
 29. Cf. Wiebe Nauta, "A Moral Critique of Fieldwork," in Ananta Kumar Giri et al.(eds.)*The Development of Religion and the Religion of Development*, CW Delft: Eburon Delft, 2004. Pp.89-100, p. 90.
 30. Cf. Rudiger Kroff & Heiko Schrader, "Does the End of Development Revitalise History?" in Ananta Kumar Giri et al. *The Development of Religion and the Religion of Development*, 9-17, p.12.
 31. *Ibid.*
 32. *Ibid.*, p.14.
 33. Cf. John Mohan Razu, "Introduction," Bangalore Theological Forum, 3&4 (30), 1998, *A Special Issue on Development*. pp 2-6.
 34. Cf. Bas de Gaay Forman, "In Search for a New Paradigm" in Ananta Kumar Giri et al. *The Development of Religion and the Religion of Development*, pp. 18-28.
 35. Cf. Ananta Kumar Giri, *New Horizons of Social Theory*, pp.199-222.
 36. G. Aloysius, *Religion as Emancipatory Identity*, New Age Publishers, New Delhi, 1998. p. 10.
 37. *Ibid.*, p. 11.
 38. Cf. As noted by Bhaduri, *Of Public Spheres*, p. 88. See also, Madhu Kanna, "The Ritual Capsule of Durga Puja: An Ecological Perspective," in Christopher Key Chapple et al. (eds.) *Hinduism and Ecology: The Intersection of Earth, Sky, and Water*, Oxford University Press, New Delhi, 2001.
 39. Sullivan, "Preface" to John A. Grim ed., *Indigenous Traditions and Ecology, Centre for the Study of World Religions*, Harvard University School, Massachusetts, Cambridge, 2001, p.xi.